

THE ROLE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE ORGANIZATION OF DISTANCE EDUCATION

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Abstract: In the article, the main goal of fundamental reforms in the field of education today is to impart knowledge based on world standards and to introduce modern educational methods in the training of competitive personnel. Therefore, distance learning has become an integral part of the modern and increasingly developing education system. The distance education system is a system updated and reworked with today's modern knowledge, in which special attention is paid to the theoretical and practical aspects of science.

Key words: distance education, information technology, digital technology, video lesson, online lecture, electronic education.

Distance education is an independent form of education, and information technology is the main tool of this education system. Distance education is an educational complex based on the exchange of educational information at a distance, the use of a special educational environment for the teacher, and the means of providing educational services to all levels of learners and foreign students. Distance education has its own characteristics, pedagogical system, purpose and necessity [1].

Digital technologies, information and communication technologies that are growing every hour, computer programs and programming languages, mathematical models and other data-based learning provide opportunities for good temporal organization. Digital technologies play an important role in the growth and development of distance education and play a role in the following key areas[2]:

1. Online preparation and distribution of teaching materials: Digital technologies make it easier for teachers and textbook authors to prepare and distribute teaching materials online. It allows sharing between teachers and learners through computers.
2. Interactive educational programs and tasks: Digital technologies are used to create interactive educational programs and tasks. Students learn and master skills easily through these tools.
3. Video lessons and online lectures: Video lessons and online lectures turn out to be a convenient and effective part of distance education. Students can see the

teachers and their lectures on their own time and help them to understand the material better.

4. Opportunity to learn at random times: Digital technologies allow students to learn at random times. This makes it easier for students to adapt and master their learning at their own time.

5. Monitoring and evaluation: Digital technologies provide convenient tools for monitoring learning processes and evaluating students. This helps to evaluate the learning outcomes and adapt the education to the new routes.

6. Special programs and platforms: Special educational programs and platforms make distance learning easier and more effective through programs designed for teachers and students.

7. Information Security: Digital technologies provide tools that are essential for keeping students' personal information safe and ensuring information security on learning platforms.

This, digital technologies show themselves in the implementation of distance education and increase student learning. Digital technologies facilitate learning and make the learning process of students more effective.

There are several positive aspects of the distance learning method[3]:

1. Creative teaching environment. Based on the created methods, the teacher imparts knowledge, and the student reads only the given material during the lesson. Based on the proposed distance learning, the students themselves search for the necessary information from a large number of electronic information resources on the basis of computer tools and, of course, share the results of their conclusions with others through various public electronic networks. This helps students to learn independently and ensures that students are always in contact with each other.

2. The possibility of independent education. Learning based on the distance method includes elementary, secondary, secondary-special, higher, part-time - evening and advanced training stages. It is important for professors and teachers to work on the basis of their personal work plans and to collect them in one electronic resource, as the main resource for students to use at any time and environment, and contribute to their independent education.

When creating a pedagogical framework in distance education, the following should be taken as a basis:

- 1) implementation of electronic education;
- 2) learning and teaching;
- 3) support and evaluation of students

4) support and evaluation of teachers

Among pedagogical technologies, the most interesting for distance education are technologies aimed at group work of students, cooperative learning, active cognitive process and working with various information sources[4].

It is through these technologies that the widespread use of problem-based methods, the application of knowledge in groups or independently, is the development of not only independent critical thinking, but also the culture of communication and the thirst for knowledge. Also, these technologies help students solve educational problems in the most effective ways.

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